

HISTORY OF ART

"SOCIO-POLITICAL PROCESSES AND THEIR INFLUENCE ON THE ARTISTIC SPHERE OF CENTRAL ASIA IN THE 20TH CENTURY: IN THE CONTEXT OF THE CREATIVE HERITAGE OF URAL TANSYKBAEV"

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Abstract

The article examines the socio-political processes of the 20th century that influenced the development of fine art in Central Asia.

Particular attention is paid to Soviet cultural policy, the formation of the art education system, the establishment of socialist realism as an official method, as well as the role of urbanization and industrialization in the transformation of the artistic sphere.

The analysis focuses on the creative legacy of Ural Tansykbayev, one of the leading representatives of the fine arts of Uzbekistan, whose formation and artistic path are closely linked to the aforementioned processes.

Keywords: Central Asia, fine arts, Soviet cultural policy, socialist realism, art education.

Introduction

The fine arts of Central Asia in the 20th century were formed in a dynamic and largely conflictual field of socio-political transformations initiated by the Soviet government. These transformations affected institutional (the creation of art schools, museums, exhibition venues), ideological (the standardization of artistic language within the framework of socialist realism) and socio-cultural (urbanization, industrialization, cultural unification and the construction of "national forms") dimensions of artistic life.

One of the most prominent representatives of the region's artistic scene was Ural Tansykbayev (1904–1974), whose work embodied a synthesis of national-local traditions and new aesthetic principles dictated by the times.

His professional biography - from studying in studios in Tashkent and Penza to participation in union exhibitions and institutional recognition - is indicative of the understanding of the "Soviet project" in the art of Central Asia, which, while remaining ideologically motivated, allowed for the variability of local artistic solutions [1].

In this article, based on domestic and foreign research, we examine the key areas of influence of macro-processes on the artistic sphere of the region and relate them to the creative legacy of U. Tansykbayev.

Historiographic review and methodology

The historiography of the issue consists of several complementary arrays.

Firstly, this is the Soviet and post-Soviet art history tradition, where the central place is occupied by the

descriptive and biographical school (M.S. Kagan, I.I. Martynenko, V.I. Maltsev, Sh. Nazarov, etc.).

These works record institutional history, key milestones in artistic policy and creative biographies of artists.

Secondly, there is an increasingly visible body of foreign research examining Soviet cultural policy in Central Asia in terms of the "spectacular state," modernization utopias, and urban transformations (L. Adams, P. Stronski, S. Reed, A. Abikaeva-Tiesenhausen, and others) [2].

Finally, a separate direction is made up of interdisciplinary studies of social realism as a mode of representation, production and mediation of images (M.K. Brown, S. Reed).

Methodologically, the article relies on institutional analysis, iconology and a contextual approach that combines the consideration of artistic form with the reconstruction of the social conditions of its production.

Soviet cultural policy and the tasks of art

In the 1920s and 1930s, an active policy of cultural construction was launched in Central Asia, aimed at forming a "new Soviet man". Art was seen as a means of ideological education, which led to tighter control over the artistic process, centralization of management structures, and canonization of images of labor, industry, and friendship between peoples. Since 1934, socialist realism has been established as the official method, requiring "a truthful, historically concrete depiction of reality in its revolutionary development" [3]. Foreign studies clarify the mechanisms of symbolic politics: as L. Adams notes, "a spectacular state is one where, more

than in most countries, politics is conducted at a symbolic level." This focus on "spectacularity" (mass celebrations, exhibitions, representative ensembles) directly influenced artistic assignments, setting a hierarchy of genres and thematic priorities.

Creation of a system of art education and professionalization

The key factor in the institutionalization of the artistic environment of Central Asia was the network of studios, schools and institutes of arts in the cities of Tashkent, Frunze and Alma-Ata, which developed in the 1920s and 1930s. It ensured the training of national personnel and their inclusion in the all-Union professional community through unified programs, traveling exhibitions and creative missions.

In the example of U. Tansykbaev, we observe a typical trajectory: classes in Tashkent studios with masters of the Russian school, training at the Penza Art School, participation in exhibition activities starting in the late 1920s [4].

It was the educational infrastructure that became the channel for the transit of aesthetic models (from the late Itinerants to Post-Impressionism), which the artist creatively reworked, adapting to local subjects and color schemes.

Ideological canons and practice of socialist realism

Socialist realism functioned not only as a stylistic norm, but also as a set of institutions—commissions, committees, exhibitions, expert assessments, criticism—regulating the production and circulation of images. S. Reed shows that the criteria of socialist realism were determined through the "feedback" of practices, where the success of specific decisions was institutionally reinforced and reproduced as a norm [5].

This logic was particularly evident in the large exhibition projects of the mid-1930s. For Central Asian artists, it meant, on the one hand, the need for thematic mobilization (industry, collectivization, "friendship of peoples"), and on the other, it opened up a space for national imagery in line with the formula "national in form, socialist in content."

The creative language of U. Tansykbaev – a generalized form, rich color, an emphasis on epic panorama – demonstrates precisely this model of correspondence, where the local landscape and ethnographic motifs are integrated into the optimistic narrative of modernization [6].

Urbanization, industrialization and the transformation of visual experience

The 20th century brought large-scale urban and infrastructural changes to Central Asia: the formation of industrial hubs, railway arteries, and new public spaces. P. Stronski, analyzing Tashkent in the 1930s–1960s, shows that the image of the "union showcase of the East" was created through targeted urban planning programming, the culmination of which was the post-war reconstruction and especially the transformations after the 1966 earthquake [7].

As the researcher emphasizes, "the official press also exposed a great deal of information on the difficulties that the state encountered in forging this socialist city", which sheds light on the contradictory nature of the modernization project. In the artistic system, this

generated a demand for new urban and industrial motifs, for the representation of infrastructural "modernity".

Tansykbaev's landscape, while preserving the poetics of open spaces, gradually includes signs of urbanization, but interprets them in the context of harmonizing man and nature, which allowed him to go beyond the limits of straightforward officialdom [8].

National and universal in the aesthetics of Ural Tansykbaev

The creative system of U. Tansykbaev is formed at the intersection of three lines: (1) local-national imagery (the color of Central Asia, motifs of nomadic culture, architectural silhouettes), (2) principles of composition and drawing learned in academic school, (3) modernist sensitivity to color and plane, actualized by post-impressionist experience [9]. The coloristic richness and decorativeness of the early period, noted by researchers, evolves into a large generalized form of the 1950s–1960s, where the landscape becomes the bearer of the value meanings of the socialist era. The rethinking of the genre hierarchy - the shift in emphasis from the multi-figure genre scene to the epic landscape - is consistent with S. Reed's observation that the leading position in the "pantheon" of socialist realism was taken by the picture of action and history, while the "quiet genre" remained marginal for a long time. At the same time, Tansykbaev's landscape acquires the qualities of a "grand style", acting as a space of collective memory and a utopian future.

"The Thaw", artistic shifts and late Tansykbaev

The period of the 1950s and 1960s, associated with de-Stalinization and the liberalization of cultural policy, marked important shifts in visual language: the range of motifs expanded, didactic rhetoric weakened, and the position of regional schools strengthened. During this same period, Tansykbaev achieved high institutional recognition (People's Artist of the USSR, member of the USSR Academy of Arts), and his landscape formula received international confirmation (silver medal at the World Exhibition in Brussels, 1958) [10].

These factors secure the artist's status as a classic of the Uzbek school, whose legacy is becoming an important resource for the region's contemporary museum and exhibition narrative (memorial museums, retrospectives, restoration programs).

Case observations: themes, motives, techniques

Without going into the attribution specifics of individual works, we will outline the typologically stable features of his language.

Firstly, the "high horizon" and panoramic composition allow us to create epic images of the steppe and mountain ranges;

secondly, the active role of local color (ocher, ultramarine, deep green), setting the emotional tone;

thirdly, the combination of an architectural motif with a natural massif as a visual formula for the harmony of tradition and modernization.

In the 1950s and 1960s, this formula stabilized, turning into a recognizable "signature" of the master,

simultaneously corresponding to the ideological demand for optimism and preserving individual poetics [11].

Institutional biography and canonization

U. Tansykbaev's institutional career reflects the mechanisms of the Soviet system of artistic titles and exhibition policy: membership in the Union of Artists of Uzbekistan since the early 1930s, election to the USSR Academy of Arts, award of the title of People's Artist of the USSR (1963) [12]. The master's works were exhibited in leading collections (State Tretyakov Gallery, State Museum of Historical Art) and regional museums, and a house-museum of the artist was created in Tashkent as an element of memorialization and regional cultural policy.

In foreign discourse, Tansykbaev is considered a key figure in the Uzbek landscape, through which the evolution of the "national" can be traced in the context of Soviet modernization [13].

Synthesis: macroprocesses and individual poetics

The socio-political vectors considered – cultural policy, institutional professionalization, urbanization and ideological canons – are not limited to external frameworks, but are part of the fabric of artistic language.

Tansykbaev's contribution to the region's art lies not only in creating iconic images of Uzbekistan, but also in demonstrating how the "national" can become the universal language of Soviet modernism.

This experience is particularly relevant for contemporary studies of post-Soviet art in Central Asia, where the revision of the Soviet legacy continues – from museum exhibition policy to current artistic practices [14].

Conclusion

The socio-political processes of the 20th century – Soviet cultural policy, the institutionalization of art education, the establishment of socialist realism and urban transformations – played a key role in the formation of the artistic sphere of Central Asia.

The creative biography and artistic language of Ural Tansykbaev allow us to see how these processes were integrated into the practice of the regional school, generating models that simultaneously meet ideological expectations and preserve local identity.

The use of foreign literature (L. Adams, P. Stronski, S. Reed, etc.) complements the domestic perspective, moving the conversation from the plane of the normative history of style to the plane of analysis of institutions, urban scenarios, and modes of representation.

It is at this intersection – between politics, the city and artistic form – that the uniqueness of 20th-century Central Asian art emerges, of which Ural Tansykbaev was a prominent representative [15].

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